

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF YOUTH TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE PROCESS OF HEALTHY WORLD VIEW AND EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8437432>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 02-October 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 06-October 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 13-October 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

ABSTRACT

Tourism entered the 21st century as a socio-economic system that has a significant impact on the world economy. According to the information of world tourism organizations, it makes up 10% of the production and service turnover in the world. If we pay attention to the world scene today, we can see that international tourism and domestic tourism are strong exports of goods and services. Tourism is the study of history, getting to know other nations and peoples, and enjoying their cultural monuments. , is also an economic flow.

In order to carry out this activity, each country should train qualified personnel and experts, as well as meet the needs of the country's population and tourism resources. If we refer to the past period, attention to tourism in Japan and China was at a very low level. Outbound and inbound touristic potential was almost not formed in these countries. Because most of the population is engaged in agriculture. Today, these countries are among the most attractive regions of tourism. Every tourist area, every country and city strives to use tourism resources wisely for economic benefit and income. As the desire is strong, climbing to the top requires effort. The specific political orientations, economic views, and the traditions and values of the society of any country play an important role in its development. To take a leading role in the tourism system it is necessary to take into account the problems and shortcomings of local residents who receive foreign tourists. It is necessary to adapt the incoming tourist activity and the host environment. If the disparity coefficient shows a large difference, tourism may not be realized. In this case, tourism requires a lifestyle of socio-economic and cultural potential of the population.

ⁱ Today, attention to domestic and foreign tourism in our country is becoming a more urgent issue. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2018

"On additional organizational measures to

create favorable conditions for the development of the tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan" is a clear proof of this.

As one of the most important factors of socio-economic development, the decree provided for the implementation of various practical activities in order to rapidly develop domestic tourism, to acquaint citizens with the cultural and historical heritage and natural resources of our country.

Taking into account that 60% of the population of our country are young people, we should understand that the development of youth tourism is one of the most pressing issues today. Because today's youth is the main layer that determines the perspective and future of tomorrow. The economic development of the country, especially the development of tourism, is in the hands of young people. There are some shortcomings in the organization of youth tourism in our country.

Abu Nasr Farabi - "The transformation of forces into action is realized with the help of experience. A person who, after conducting an experiment, is mistaken in thinking about the opposite of the true nature of things in these experiments and actions, is not perfect, but the one who gains the most experience in this work is the most honorable and the most perfect person." - he says. In today's era of economic growth, it is necessary to discover a new way based on experiences rather than contradictions.

What issues should be paid attention to in order to develop youth tourism in Uzbekistan?

In this case, taking the following practical actions will determine the starting point of the goal. That is, the study of the evolution of tourism and the analysis of the situation of the young people in it. Today there are young people from different walks of life in our society. We will divide them into the following content and types:

- 1) young people with full socio-economic potential;
- 2) young people with poor socio-economic opportunities;
- 3) young people in need of social and economic assistance;
- 4) young people living in the non-industrialized part of the region;
- 5) young people who are economic providers in the family;
- 6) young people deprived of parental support.

If we connect the above classification to each other and give it a practical tone, the potential of becoming one of the mature individuals who have their place in the society shows a high indicator if young people of every stratum use the opportunities created more.

Here, another important factor is the initial stage in the creation of youth tourism in our country - coverage of different classes in terms of age:

- 1) children in preschool educational institutions;
- 2) school-aged children;
- 3) young people in higher education.

Today, the development of youth tourism in our country is important not only from the point of view of its impact on the country's economy, but also on the education of young people. This can be justified as follows:

Firstly, to develop a sense of knowledge of history and interest in material and cultural heritage;

Secondly, spending the free time of young people effectively;

Thirdly, to realize the true essence of the rich spiritual heritage of the great scholars of our country;

Fourth, prevention of joining extremist and terrorist groups;

Fifth, to form the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland;

Sixth, practical development of knowledge and skills from various disciplines (geography, psychology, ethnography, law, economics, informatics);

Seventh, to strengthen feelings of national pride and pride.

Therefore, the program "Travel around Uzbekistan" should be used for the younger generations first.

We believe that it is appropriate to use the following effective methods of youth tourism development:

The first method is to publish material, cultural and spiritual monuments of our country in the form of a collection of books for children in pre-school educational institutions and prepare cartoons about it;

The second method is to prepare video discs about historical monuments and great scientists in the textbooks of students studying at school, that is, live and reliable delivery of the topics covered by the textbook;

The third method is to organize various festivals in important places in cities, districts, and villages;

The fourth method is to gradually organize competitions among young people and introduce the "Travel around Uzbekistan" ticket to the winners;

The fifth method is to create a charity fund and organize 24-hour trips in order to increase the educational potential of young people and children living in the most remote areas and to awaken the spirit of social equality and indifference to the fate of the nation;

The sixth method is to make videos about historical monuments, material and spiritual heritage for pre-school education, secondary and general education, as well as higher education institutions and present them to regular young people.

In conclusion, as the philosopher-poet Bedil said: "If the first stone of the building's foundation is laid crookedly, even if the building's head reaches the stars, it will remain crooked." We hope that the above methods will determine the correct and purposeful development of youth tourism in Uzbekistan, as well as the development stage of the educational process.

Also, youth tourism has a significant impact on the social, cultural and educational spheres of the country. Respecting the dreams and hopes of the whole society and creating an environment based on fairness, mutual understanding among people, mutual trust among young people and a high level of loyalty to the country will serve as a factor. Also, young people should be able to carry out touristic activities, employment, social and economic self-fulfillment, perfect knowledge of the area they live in, interest in historical monuments in our country, love for the spiritual heritage of the Allamas. shapes them.

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ⁱ <https://arxiv.uz>

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